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A Creative Folio

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The Real Tea On Hospitality

It is nice to work in hotels,
Almost like living in one,
Where faces from all nations pass,
And luxury greets the sun.

Prestigious chains, a shining name,
A glamour hard to miss,
Yet behind the glow and polished halls,
Lie trials deep as this.

The hours are so long,
Especially on holidays near,
Peak seasons press with heavy weight,
The pressure is always clear.

A single rest day, sometimes two,
But most will only gain one,
The pay depends on where you stand,
Big chains or budget-run.

Feet grow sore from endless work,
Standing all day through,
And if the team is far from kind,
The burden doubles, too.

But the hardest challenge of them all,
It is not the work alone,
It's guests who are treated with little care,
As if hearts were made of stone.

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Entitled voices, sharp demands,
Tantrums when denied,
Forgetting that staff are human too,
With dignity and pride.

Yet many still endure it all,
For salary or need,
While others leave to find a path
Where hearts and souls are freed.